

JOURNAL OF ENGLISH STUDIES

ISSN : 3122-0479

DOI – <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18036615>

Volume 1 No 1 December (2025): Journal of English Studies

**ENDANGERING INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA: A
STUDY OF LANGUAGE USE BY YORUBA-SPEAKING STUDENTS AT SELECTED
SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OYO STATE**

<https://joesfudutsinma.com.ng/joes/index.php/one/article/view/12>

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of social media on the declining use of indigenous Yoruba language among students of selected secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State, Southwestern Nigeria. Mixed methods: qualitative and quantitative methods were adopted in this study. Paired-depth interview and survey method were used to investigate the determinants for the decline in the use of Yoruba language and the ways social media has contributed to the decline. Findings show that cultural imperialism is the effect of social media on the declining use of indigenous language among students of secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area. Findings also show that the official use of the English language as a medium of instruction and teaching in all schools is a major determinant of the declining use of Yoruba language in Atiba Local Government Area. Youths in the southwest geo-political Zone who are regular users of the internet and social media must be made to understand the importance of using the Yoruba language in sharing and exchanging information on social media networks and sites. A policy, as a matter of urgency, should be made to create a Lingua Franca to be used as a language of teaching and instructions in all levels of education in the South-West.

Key Words: *Endangerment, Language Abandonment, Social Media Discourse, Students, Yoruba Language*

Introduction

Social media presents a platform for the users to interact, share ideas and reinforce the dominant representation of indigenous language (Balogun, 2023). Social media has become a game changer among speakers of the Yoruba Language in Oyo State (Arulchelvan *et al.*, 2019). Apart from its use for entertainment, information-sharing and distant communication process, social media has

been identified to influence the language of indigenous speakers of Yoruba. Language is a veritable means of communication among the indigenous habitants of a community (Badmus, 2020). The Yoruba language is a dominant language spoken by the people in the South-West geo-political zone of Nigeria. Studies reveal that indigenous language plays a crucial role in the cognitive development of humans. There are four varieties of indigenous Yoruba Language in the Southwestern Nigeria: standard Yoruba Language (such as the one spoken in Oyo town of Oyo State), indigenous Yoruba Language (this is spoken by all indigenes of the Southwestern Nigeria), ethnic indigenous Yoruba Language (this is spoken by different Yoruba indigenous groups and minorities), and generational indigenous Yoruba Language (Egele and Ugheoke, 2023). The link between language, family, educational pursuit, community, politics, commerce and economy is much profound (Malcolm *et al.*, 2020). Indigenous language is a symbol of identity of a group of people. There are several factors that are responsible for abandonment of indigenous language. Getting a new job in an urban centre, adoption of a foreign language as a medium of communication at a workplace and using a foreign language as a medium of instruction and information transmission to children at home all contribute to language abandonment. Intercultural marriage and moving abroad in search of greener pasture also contribute to the decline of an indigenous language (Egele and Ugheoke, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

Indigenous language serves as the primary medium of communication among people in the South-Western Nigeria, influencing social interactions, cultural expressions, and the means of identity formation (DavTyan, 2024). While some scholars argued that social media has supported the revitalization of indigenous languages, others claimed that social media has aided the extinction

of indigenous languages in Africa (Ligidima and Makananise, 2020). The widespread use of social media as a means of communication, entertainment, interaction, information and education among youths has challenged and questioned the traditional practices, knowledge systems and indigenous language that have sustained the indigenous communities from time immemorial (Davtyan, 2024). With the pervasive use of English as a medium of information, education and entertainment, Yoruba is endangered and parent-child intergenerational transmission of indigenous Yoruba has become poor in most households in the South-Western Nigeria. Speakers of indigenous languages in Africa are reduced every day and the same can be said of the Yoruba of the South-Western Nigeria (Davtyan, 2024).

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. understand the determinants for the declining use of Yoruba among students of select secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area;
2. determine the roles of Yoruba Language teachers in the revitalisation of indigenous Yoruba Language among students of select secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area;
3. ascertain ways social media has affected the proficient use of indigenous Yoruba language among students of select secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area; and

4. know the factors that are responsible for the preference of foreign language to indigenous languages among students of select secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area.

Literature Review

Parental abandonment of the Yoruba language as a medium of education and training at home endangers the sustenance of the Yoruba language. Buttressing the foregoing, Oluyemi and Olumide (2024) found that weak parental responsibilities, prohibition of indigenous language at homes and in schools, western influence, cultural imperialism, peer influence, social media and the internet are the causes of decline in the use of indigenous language among secondary students. The prevalence of social media and high propensity of using the medium for information sharing have weakened the proficient use of the Yoruba language among young people. Omoro *et al.*, (2021) found that social media has enhanced the channels of information sharing and communication process, its use should be subjected to censorship and cultural suitability test to preserve indigenous language and cherished traditional values in Africa. Egele and Ugheoke (2023) found that the language used for information and communication technology is assured of growth and development and can never go into extinction unlike indigenous language that are not used for technological information-sharing. Ekwueme and Rosemary (2019) found that social media users should make use of their indigenous language for information, education and entertainment to prevent its extinction. Lamb and Coleman (2008) found that language propagated by government, required as a criterion for qualification for an employment, used for educational purposes in schools, spoken at homes by parents, and used for the reportage of news and other information by the mass media survives external onslaught and influence.

Intergenerational use of indigenous language prevents its death. The advent of globalization and, information and communication technology and social media have greatly impacted the level of

usage of indigenous language in Africa (Egele and Ugheoke, 2023). When a language is lost, an essential part of an indigenous cultural practice is lost among members of a community. When a native language is abandoned, cultural practices of thousands of years become extinct (Egele and Ugheoke, 2023). Yoruba-speaking youths of this century use social media to anglicize their names and find no values and honour in the use of indigenous names (Ajepe and Ademowo, 2016). The transmission of cultural heritage from older generation to younger generation strengthens the use of indigenous language in a community. There are various determinants of linguistic extinction a community of its speakers. The emergence and widespread use of social media for communication, entertainment, information and education have impacted the visibility and effective use of indigenous language in Nigeria (Balogun, 2023). Research findings have shown that many indigenous languages are on the march to extinction because of the decline of its users and speakers. Social media, as a global medium of communication, enables students to have access to global culture and international academic best global practices (Malcolm et al., 2020).

Indigenous language represents a medium by which cultural identities of a group of people are negotiated, affirmed and transformed within indigenous communities of Africa (Davtyan, 2024). While language is a very important tool for the attainment of development goals in developing nations, many of the speakers of the indigenous languages in Africa have systematically jettisoned the preference for the foreign languages such as English and French. To achieve behavioural change and persuade people to embrace certain policies of government, indigenous language has been found to play a crucial role. Social media has marginalized, devalued, disabled indigenous languages, knowledge system and cultural identities among Africans (GandoIfo, 2009). Rather than embrace their indigenous language and culture, youths in Africa widely promote the use of English on social media. The use of English on social media, as a medium of global

communication, has posed a serious challenge to the use of indigenous language as a means of information-sharing, education and entertainment in Nigeria (Ekwueme and Rosemary, 2019). Thus, social media has brought about a decline in the use of indigenous language in many Nigerian communities. The predominant use of English on social media and its increasing ascendancy has stunted the growth of over 529 indigenous languages in Nigeria (Ajepe and Ademowo, 2016).

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on technological determinism theory. This theory was propounded by Thorsten Veblen in the 1960s. The use of technological determinism theory is dependent on explanation of technological influence on cultural belief and language in contemporary times. The growing popularity of social media among youths has altered the competent use of Yoruba among students of secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State, southwestern Nigeria. Technological determinism theory assumes that technology is a determinant factor of societal changes and social transformations. Social media technology does not only affect our attitude or behaviour, but also affects the most vital aspect of culture-language. Advocates of technological determinism theory opine that social changes are influenced by the technological development and communication technology (Hauer, 2017). TDT explains relationship between the technology of social media and ways social media users are affected by frequent exposure to global domination of English, which decreases their capability in the proficient use of indigenous Yoruba as a means of communication in their localities (Jan et al., 2020). Social media has penetrated all spheres of our lives, including language and cultural practices. Social media is used to converse with people irrespective of their geographical locations or boundaries. Unlike the conventional media known to give prominence to the Yoruba language in their news analysis and reportage, social media technology contributes to the declining use of Yoruba in South-Western Nigeria. This theory is

appropriate to the study because it explains ways technological determinism theory has affected the use of indigenous language through social media technology in so many ways.

Research Methodology

The study made use of a mixed method: qualitative and quantitative methods. Paired-depth interview and survey method were used. The study was conducted in select secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area. The secondary schools selected are Alaafin High School and Bode Thomas Memorial Grammar Schools. The researchers sampled the opinions and views of Yoruba Language teachers on the determinants of the declining use of indigenous Yoruba Language and the roles of Yoruba Language teachers in the revitalisation of indigenous Yoruba Language, while opinions of the senior secondary students in class three were sampled on the ways social media has affected the proficient use of indigenous Yoruba Language and the factors that are responsible for the preference of foreign language to indigenous Yoruba Language among students of select secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area.

The population of the study borders on all the senior secondary students in Class Three in all the two selected secondary schools and two teachers of Yoruba Language in each of the two secondary schools were purposively selected for the study. However, it is hardly possible to use all the senior students in Class Three. Therefore, the sample size was taken from the population of the students. Researchers ensured that students who were exposed to the dominance of English Language on social media were selected for the study. The students were given copies of questionnaire to fill. Yoruba Language teachers who are familiar with the influence of social media on proficient use of indigenous language were also selected for the paired-depth interview session. The secondary schools were selected due to geographical locations to the researchers and the willingness of the students and teachers of Yoruba Language to participated in the study. The respondents were not

under any pressure to participate in the study. Objectives of the study were appropriately explained to them before they were given copies of the questionnaire or got interviewed by the researchers. Two research assistants were recruited to help in the administration of questionnaire to Class Three senior secondary students in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State. With regard to paired-depth interview, two Yoruba Teachers were selected in each of the two secondary school for the paired-depth interview session.

Students from whom data were gathered and the teachers who were subjected to paired-depth interview in the two secondary schools were purposively selected for the study. The principals of the two selected secondary schools were contacted and their permission was secured before the questionnaire was administered on the students. The consent of the Yoruba Language teachers in the two secondary schools was also sought and secured before the paired-depth interview session was initiated. The two categories of respondents were not under any compulsion to participate in the study. The respondents were assured of the information given during interview. The respondents' identities were not disclosed either by their names or addresses after the interview session. Four teachers of Yoruba Language were slated for the interview in all the two selected secondary schools. Using Taro Yamane 1967 sample size procedure, 400 students of senior secondary school Class Three were given 400 copies of questionnaire to fill. Of the 400 copies of questionnaire administered on the respondents, 389 copies of questionnaire were returned and found useable by the researchers.

Interview guide and questionnaire were developed by the researchers to collect data from the relevant respondents. The interview guide and the questionnaire were shared with Yoruba Teachers of the selected senior secondary schools for their suggestions and inputs. The instruments were

also shared with language experts for their inputs and suggestions before the final administration of the instruments to respondents.

Data Analysis

Data gathered through paired-depth interview were vetted and read by researchers many times to ensure that are in sync with research objectives. Data obtained through paired-depth interview were analysed and interpreted using explanation building and also analysed thematically in line with objectives of the study. Data collected through questionnaire were analysed with the use of frequency and percentage.

Results

Qualitative Data Analysis, Interpretations and Presentation

3.1 Theme 1: Determinants of the Declining Use of Indigenous Language among Students of Senior Secondary Schools

Data from the paired-depth interview showed determinants of the declining use of indigenous language among students of senior secondary school. The discussions revealed that the official use of English Language as a medium of instruction and teaching in all schools is a major determinant of the declining use of indigenous language in Atiba Local Government Area. Giving more insights about determinants of declining use of indigenous language, a teacher of Yoruba Language at Alaafin High School, said:

The official use of English Language as a medium of instruction and teaching in all schools is a major determinant of the declining use of indigenous language in Atiba Local Government Area. When you look at the crop of secondary school students

these days, they can hardly speak indigenous Yoruba Language. Even at home, the only language used by parents to pass information and instructions to their children remains English Language. Besides, English Language is also the language of advertising, media, music, movies, and the internet. The exposure of young ones to dominant use of English Language on the internet, music and foreign movies have contributed in no small measure to the declining use of indigenous Yoruba Language. To combat the declining use of indigenous Yoruba Language, Nollywood must be made to promote the use of indigenous Yoruba Language through the use of Yoruba Language to produce films for public consumption. Policies must also be emplaced to teach some subjects such as Mathematics, Biology and Agricultural Science using indigenous Yoruba Language. A day must be set aside in a week when students should compulsorily speak indigenous Yoruba Language in all their academic activities.

Another paired-depth interview participant, who is a teacher of Yoruba Language at Bode Thomas Memorial Secondary School, said:

The declining use of indigenous Yoruba Language has the connivance of the telecommunication service providers, parents and the social media and internet. Telecommunication service providers message and communicate with their customers, both literate and the illiterate using a dominant English Language, which many of them hardly understand. Even the youths are used to receiving the messages and communication from telecommunication service providers in English. Google offers its messages in English. Social media and the internet are also accessed through the use of English. But in all these, parents are most culpable.

Many illiterate parents would compel their wards to speak English Language at all cost because they perceive that there is prestige attached to speaking English Language at the expense of indigenous Yoruba Language. Scholars of Linguistics have found that to be a better speaker of Language 2, which is the foreign English Language, one must be a better speaker of Language 1, which is the mother tongue or indigenous Yoruba Language. Even in religious and worship centres, English Language is employed as a medium of communication to the detriment of indigenous Yoruba Language. Thus, failing to speak indigenous Yoruba Language is losing one's important component of one's culture- indigenous Yoruba Language.

3.2 Theme 2: The Roles of Yoruba Language Teachers in the Revitalisation of Indigenous Language

Data from the paired-depth interview showed the roles of Yoruba Language teachers in the revitalisation of indigenous language. The discussions revealed that we have the responsibility of sensitising the media founders and owners that indigenous Yoruba Language programmes should be done or anchored more on mass media such as radio, television than English Language programmes. Giving more insights about roles of Yoruba Language teachers in revitalising indigenous language, a teacher of Yoruba Language at Bode Thomas Memorial Grammar School, said:

The roles of Yoruba Language teachers are very vital in the revitalisation of Indigenous Yoruba Language. First, in all our classroom situations, we must allow the students to know the importance of studying Yoruba Language even at the tertiary institution level be it College of Education, Polytechnic or University. The

sustenance and use of indigenous use of Yoruba Language is largely dependent on intergenerational learning of the language. Besides, we have the responsibility of sensitising the media founders and owners that indigenous Yoruba Language programmes should be done or anchored more on mass media such as radio, television than English Language programmes. We also have a responsibility to sensitise the people that national Dailies such as the Punch Newspaper, The Tribune, The Vanguard, The Nation must have the indigenous Yoruba Language version of the newspapers for the wide circulation of their contents. As Yoruba Language teachers, we make sure that our students speak indigenous Yoruba Language during our classes.

Another paired-depth interview participant, who is a teacher of Yoruba Language at Alaafin High School, said:

The roles of indigenous Yoruba Language teachers are varied and manifold. Yoruba Language, as a subject is not made compulsory by some state government in the South West, including History subject. We have spoken in many conferences and fora that government cannot expect social vices, kidnapping armed robbery, cattle rustling, burglary and other security issues to reduce when the most valuable medium of combating these challenges are waved off. Through indigenous Yoruba Language, the importance of honesty, hard work, shame associated with being a burglar, an armed robber, a thief is expressed or taught using indigenous Yoruba Language. We are fast losing our cultural practices through cultural imperialism, and foreign movie and internet are the major means of cultural subjugation of weaker cultural practices in developing nations like Nigeria. even in sports, English

language is used by local coaches in place of indigenous Yoruba Language. As a teacher, I have recommended the use of indigenous Yoruba Language as a medium of sports coaching. I have also suggested in different fora that State Governors of the South-West should address people of their states in indigenous Yoruba Language.

Quantitative Data Analysis, Interpretation and Presentation

Table One: Effects of Social Media on the Proficient Use of Indigenous Language

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Declining use of indigenous language among youths who are heavy users of social Media.	148	38%
The use of English as a medium of global Information, entertainment and education	46	11.8%
Cultural imperialism	163	41.9%
Subtle psychological subjugation of Youths who are the heavy users of social media	32	8.3%
Total	389	100

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025

Table 1 shows that 148 respondents representing 38% averred that declining use of indigenous language is the effect of social media on the proficient use of the Yoruba language among students of secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area, 46 respondents representing 11.8% maintained that the use of English as a medium of global information, entertainment and education

is the effect of social media on the proficient use of indigenous language, 163 respondents representing 41.9% stated that cultural imperialism is the effect of social media on the proficient use of indigenous language, 32 respondents representing 8.3% averred that subtle psychological subjugation of youths who are heavy users of social media is the effect of social media on the proficient use of indigenous language.

Table Two: Factors Responsible for the Preference of Foreign Language to Indigenous Languages

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Indigenous languages perpetuate ethnic Hostilities	148	38.1%
Indigenous languages keep people apart	113	29%
Indigenous languages weaken national loyalty	89	22.9%
Indigenous languages increase the danger of Separatist sentiments	39	10%
Total	389	100

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2 shows that 148 respondents representing 38.1% averred that indigenous languages perpetuate ethnic hostilities, and therefore, that is responsible for the preference of foreign language to indigenous languages, 113 respondents representing 29% maintained that indigenous languages keep people apart, and therefore, that is responsible for the preference of foreign language to indigenous languages, 89 respondents representing 22.9% affirmed that indigenous languages weaken national unity, and that is responsible for the preference of foreign language to

indigenous languages, while 39 respondents representing 10% maintained that indigenous languages increase the danger of separatist sentiments and that is responsible for the preference of foreign language to indigenous languages.

Discussions

The official use of English Language as a medium of instruction and teaching in all schools is a major determinant of the declining use of indigenous language in Atiba Local Government Area. The findings are in tandem with Ajepe and Ademowo (2016) who found that the dominant use of English Language has affected in a negative way the quality of indigenous language used by the elite. They also found that absence of Lingua Franca has weaponised English Language to become hegemonic, nurtured and widely and robustly used in the local population. English Language is adopted in all the sectors of national life as a medium of communication.

Teachers have the responsibility of sensitising the media founders and owners that indigenous Yoruba Language programmes should be done or anchored more on mass media such as radio, television than English Language programmes. The findings are in line with the position of Ajepe and Ademowo (2016) who found that government needs to make language policy that effectively promotes the use of indigenous language by the media owners and media workers. News analysis, commentaries, advertisements and interviews must be done on media using indigenous language to arrest the declining use of the indigenous language.

Cultural imperialism is the effect of social media on the proficient use of indigenous language among students of secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area. the findings are in sync with the postulations of technological determinism which explains the social media technology and ways social media users are affected by frequent exposure to global domination of English

language, which decreases their capability in the proficient use of indigenous Yoruba Language as a means of communication in their localities (Jan et al., 2020). Social media has penetrated all spheres of our lives, including language and cultural practices.

Indigenous languages perpetuate ethnic hostilities, and therefore, that is responsible for the preference of foreign language to indigenous languages. The findings are in sync with the position of Ajepe and Ademowo (2016) who found that English Language has been institutionalised as the language of integration and unity, especially in developing nations like Africa. They further found that English Language has emerged as the language without which the unity of Nigeria as a nation is almost impossible or outright impossible. They further found that English Language is a language of education, telecommunications, information and communication technology, government, economy commerce, and it is also the language of print and electronic media, including social media.

Conclusion

Indigenous language is a very vital tool of development, especially in most developing societies of Asias and Africa, where people are predominantly illiterate. English has stunted the use of indigenous language among locals in Nigeria, and by extension, Africa. When a stronger culture come in contact with a weaker culture, the weaker culture is automatically eliminated. One of ways by which a stronger culture kills a weaker culture is by taking over the indigenous languages used by the speakers away from them. The media of mass communication, foreign movies, foreign news agencies, foreign media of mass communication, social media and the internet are some of the means by which indigenous languages are eliminated among the speakers. The use of foreign language as a medium of instructions and teaching in schools and offices have also declined the use of indigenous languages among the speakers.

Recommendations

An official use of English Language, as a medium of teaching and instructions in primary, secondary and tertiary institutions, has to be re-visited. A policy, as a matter of urgency, should be made to create a Lingua Franca to be used as a language of teaching and instructions in all levels of education in the South-West. This could be done when the six state Governors in the South-Western Nigeria meet, conceive, plan and execute language policy for the development of the South-West Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria. A language policy meant for the region is necessary to hinder the declining use of the indigenous language among people.

Teachers of Yoruba Language in all the levels of education must meet regularly via conferences and forums to discuss the dangers of the declining use of the indigenous language in the South-West Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria and issue press releases at the end of such for a, conferences or meeting. Mass media owners and founders also have a role to play here. Indigenous Yoruba Language programmes must feature more on their channels than foreign programmes disseminated in English Language.

Youths in the South-West Geo-Political Zone who are heavy users of the internet and social media must be made to understand the importance of using their indigenous Yoruba Language in sharing and exchanging information on social media networks and sites. Like English, which is the language of social media and the internet, indigenous Yoruba Language must be used for social media and internet communication process among people irrespective of their geographical locations.

There are a variety of dialects within indigenous Yoruba Language in the South-West Geo-Political Zone. Therefore, a variant of indigenous Yoruba Language that is acceptable to all and sundry in

the region should be emplaced to lessen the ethnic rivalry and hostilities among different ethnic nationalities in the South-West Geo-Political Zone.

Ethical Consideration

Observing research ethics, researchers made sure that personalities and identities of paired-depth interviewees were never disclosed. Copies of questionnaire administered to respondents never contain the names and addresses of the respondents. The respondents were not under duress to participate in the study.

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